

Sterility mechanism in different TGMS and CMS lines of rice

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Thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) is a new genetic tool used in developing commercial F₁ rice hybrids. This study investigated the stage at which sterility occurs during anther development in TGMS lines. For critical examination, panicles were collected from TGMS lines TS16, TS18, TS29, and cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025A and IR62829A. In the TGMS lines, the developmental stages of young panicles were examined at stages IV, V, and VI in September 1998 and May 1999 for the expression of fertility and sterility, respectively. Anthers were taken out from the spikelet and fixed in 70% alcohol for 1 h. These were then passed through a series of solutions containing alcohol and methyl salicylate in the proportion of 4:1, 3:2, 2:3, and 1:4, and finally in methyl salicylate for 15 min in each solution with two changes in the last step. Cleared anthers were mounted in methyl salicylate in a cavity microslide and examined using a *Namarski differential interference contrast* in a bright field microscope for optimal viewing and microphotography.

Sterile anthers differed from fertile anthers in size, shape of pollen grain, and anther color in TGMS lines (see figure). In all TGMS lines, sterile anthers were small with empty pollen grains of irregular shape, except in TS16, which showed pollen-free anthers (see figure). This indicated that the sensitive stage of TS16 was at stage IV (stamen and pistil primordia) of panicle development.

A distinct variation was observed between sterile and fertile expression in anther size, shape, and color besides content and quantity of pollen grains in TS18, TS29, and CMS lines. Pollen grains of sterile anthers were small and irregu-

larly shaped, whereas fertile pollen grains were plump, larger, and yellow. This indicated that the occurrence of sterility in TS18, TS29, and CMS lines is postmeiotic. Results strongly indicate that genes governing premeiotic sterility operate in TS16, leading to the pollen-free nature of the anther, while certain other genes operate

at postmeiotic stages, causing sporophytic sterility in TS18, TS29, and CMS lines. The genetic mechanisms and variations in the developmental pattern of anther and pollen production could be clearly understood by analyzing the expression of sterility/fertility in intermated lines and the segregating progenies of TGMS lines.

Pollen-free anther in TS16 (May 1999). Sterile phase-sensitive stage—stage IV (stamen and pistil primordia of panicle development).

Fertile anthers in TS16 (September 1998). Fertile phase of TGMS line TS16.

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